

AI-ENHANCED TELE-REHABILITATION: RESEARCH-ORIENTED MODELING FOR FALL RISK, TREATMENT EFFECTIVENESS, AND ADVERSE EVENTS IN BALANCE DISORDERS

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Introduction

Balance is a critical function for human mobility and independence [1]. Balance disorders in older adults, increase fall risk and reduce quality of life, with 28-42% of adults over 65 falling annually, emphasizing the need for effective prevention strategies [2]. AI advancements are improving balance assessment and fall risk prediction [1]. Our study aims to develop and validate AI-driven models for fall risk, treatment effectiveness, and adverse events within a tele-rehabilitation context.

Materials & Methods

The study utilizes data from the TeleRehaB project, including retrospective data from the Holobalance project (HOL), the EMBalance project (EMB), and UCL, UK, covering patients aged 16-98 with balance disorders. The dataset comprises clinical, demographic, and symptom-related data. Data preprocessing involves feature encoding, imputation (Simple and Iterative), normalization, and handling of imbalanced classes via SMOTE. Multiple classifiers (XGBoost, KNN, Neural Networks, etc.) were trained using a 10-fold cross-validation strategy. Model interpretability was achieved through SHAP values to explain feature contributions. These models improve clinical decision-making and patient outcomes in rehabilitation settings by addressing key clinical endpoints, including Risk of Fall (RoF), Treatment Effectiveness (TE), and Adverse Events (AE).

Results & Discussion

The study addressed three specific clinical use cases: predicting RoF, evaluating TE, and identifying AE. Table I details models, datasets, and metrics used, with some models being particularly relevant to clinical relevance.

Table I. Results overview of Research-oriented models.

End point	Source	Target	Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Key Aspect
RoF	EMB	FALL	XGB	0.94 ± 0.06	0.93 ± 0.07	0.94 ± 0.02	Tendency to Fall
TE	UCL	HADA	XGB	0.94 ± 0.06	0.87 ± 0.10	0.87 ± 0.13	HAD
AE	HOL	SYMP TOMS	RF	0.86 ± 0.14	0.85 ± 0.13	0.80 ± 0.20	WHO DAS 7

Results show a high accuracy of 94%, using the EMB, on the RoF targeting the tendency to fall. For TE, UCL data

with HADA targets yielded 94% accuracy with XGBoost. Lastly, the RF with the HOL dataset with symptoms as the target reached an accuracy of 86% for AE. SHAP values provide insight into the influence of input variables on research-oriented models' predictions. For instance, at RoF (Figure 1), Tendency_to_fall and age are dominant drivers, with moderate influences like Dizziness emotional subscore, and Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HAD_A_D). Other features like Vertigo instability, have lower significance.

Figure 1. SHAP value for Risk of Fall.

The study demonstrates that AI models can predict critical endpoints, aid early risk stratification, guide personalized rehabilitation, and improve long-term tele-rehabilitation outcomes, but faces limitations like retrospective data and potential bias.

References

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Keywords: AI predictive analytics, Fall Risk, Treatment Effectiveness, Adverse Events, Rehabilitation

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